

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Influence of cross-training program to employee retention in selected Restaurants in Cabanatuan City Nueva Ecija

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Abstract

Restaurants are constantly looking for ways to improve the efficiency and productivity of their operations. One effective strategy is to implement a cross-training program among employees. By training staff for different tasks in the restaurant, it always ensures coverage and flexibility in case of unexpected absences or busy times. This study emphasized how Cross-Training programs affect the employees' retention. Among one hundred twenty-five (125) employees of selected Restaurants in Cabanatuan City. This research through quantitative descriptive correlational analysis technique was able to analyze the influence of cross-training program and employees' retention. Researcher were able to see what the cross-training program relationship is all about in the retention of staff. The Result of the study shows a significant relationship between Cross-training program and its effect to the growth and retention of employees. The organization should regularly engage in programs like Cross-training since it benefits the employees themselves by providing them with valuable skills and experience that can enhance their career growth within the restaurant industry. It allows them to gain a better understanding of different aspects of the business, leading to improved teamwork and communication among staff members.

Keywords: Business; Cross-training program; Employees; Influence; Retention

1. Introduction

The practice of teaching staff members to do duties other than their regular responsibilities or to operate in several roles while transferring between stations is known as a cross-training program. By doing this, organizations will be able to obtain support internally rather than having to outsource work, particularly in situations where employees with specialized talents are either absent or depart the company. Additionally, the team will be stronger, increasing the chances of employee promotions. The management of the store team conducted assessments and trainings to determine the crew's competency on a particular station to sort out the potential cross-training program.

Cross-training initiatives are critical to the hospitality sector, particularly in the restaurant industry. Many workers will develop and demonstrate their abilities to operate in various hotel and restaurant areas. If certain staff are not there, they can be more accommodating and complete some jobs at an unexpected time. It gives workers the chance to advance their careers, which is advantageous for any kind of business. The restaurant may always function more efficiently and well with the support of this form of training.

The purpose of the Cross-Training program is to prepare staff members for duties that are outside of their purview or to work in various positions. Employees benefit from it as well because they learn a new skill—flexibility at work. What is being examined is the impact of the cross-training program as the independent variable and how it influences the dependent variable. Cross-training initiatives have a significant effect on employee retention. The employee retention

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rate is the dependent variable. The ability of a company to manage fluctuations in the number of workers leaving their positions voluntarily or under duress is known as employee retention.

This study aims to document and clarify the impact of cross-training programs on employee retention, as well as to track the evolution of crew members' abilities and skills of selected restaurants in Cabanatuan city. Additionally, it seeks to observe how crew performance affects the store overall in day-to-day operations. This study's main goal is to demonstrate how training employees with varying skill sets may impact their commitment to their work and how it transforms and develops them into excellent, devoted team members for the organization.

Furthermore, this research aims to answer the following statements:

1.1. Statement of the Problem

- How may the Cross-training program in selected restaurants in Cabanatuan city be described?
- How may the Employees' retention in selected restaurants in Cabanatuan city be described?
- How may the relationship between cross-training program and Employees' retention in selected restaurants in Cabanatuan city be ascertained?

1.2. Objective of the Study

- To describe the Cross-Training Program in selected restaurants in Cabanatuan city
- To describe the Employees' retention in selected restaurants in Cabanatuan city
- To determine the relationship between Cross-Training program and Employees' retention in selected restaurants in Cabanatuan city

2. Material and methods

2.1. Participants

The personnel in selected restaurants, Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija who volunteered their time to participate in the study were the participants. The selection of personnel was based on two criteria: (1) they had to be between the ages of 18 and 30; and (2) they had to be employed by restaurants. A total of 260 responses were obtained using random sampling to choose the participants. The researcher narrowed the sample size from 260 to 125 respondents.

2.2. Research Design

A quantitative descriptive correlational analysis was used in the study to clearly show how the Cross Training Program and Employee Retention in Selected restaurants, Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija, are related. Descriptive research is a helpful choice because the purpose of research is to determine the outcomes, connections, and skill development. The quantitative method focuses on measuring policies and statistical analysis, statistics, or voting data figures, questionnaires, surveys, and computerized approaches for correcting already-existing statistical data. Establishing interactions between one object, independent factors, dependent variables, and populations is another use for quantitative research (USCLibraries, 2017).

2.3. Research Instrument

For this investigation, the researcher employed a standardized questionnaire to collect data. Self-constructed questionnaires have been used by researcher as a method to accomplish the goals of the study. The purpose of the statements was to collect data regarding the correlation between cross-training initiatives and employee retention. To formulate their conclusions about the relationship between cross-training programs and employee retention, the researcher examined the issue statement, relevant literature, and additional sources.

Two sets of questions made up the survey questionnaire, which was used to gather demographic data from the respondents. Ten (10) questions concerning the Cross-Training program for selected restaurants in Cabanatuan city personnel make up this instrument. There were ten (10) queries about employees' retention in the second section of the questionnaire. Using a four-point rating scale (1-4 from strongly disagree to strongly agree), the researcher was able to achieve a very specific and greater degree of response rate. The goal of the questionnaire and other research instruments is to gather information that will give researcher precise findings.

Table 2 Survey form Mean Score Rating and Interpretation

Rate	Range			Verbal Interpretation
1	1	-	1.75	Strongly Disagree
2	1.76	-	2.50	Disagree
3	2.51	-	3.25	Agree
4	3.26	-	4.00	Strongly Agree

The degree of internal consistency, or the degree of correlation between a set of items, is measured by Cronbach's alpha. It is identified as an indicator of scale reliability. The 20 items' rather good internal consistency is indicated by their alpha coefficient of .904. The findings of a reliability test that was used to evaluate consistency reliability and the degree of correlation between a group of items are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3 Reliability Test Results

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.904	20

2.4. Data Collection Procedure

A letter of intent was sent to conduct a survey questionnaire to selected restaurants' employees. The researcher will search and collect data from an employed individual in selected restaurant in Cabanatuan city and utilize survey questionnaires with a checklist and multiple-choice format through printed survey questionnaires. The researcher will also request permission to conduct a survey among their respondents. The relevance of the respondent's responses to the study will be explained to them when they have been given approval. Also, the researcher will collect and tailor the data for interpretation once the respondents have answered the questionnaire. Lastly, with assurances that the respondents' data collected will be confidential and will be personally inputted by the researcher.

2.5. Data Analysis Procedure

After collecting the data, the researcher extracted the data collected from printed materials and transferred in a spreadsheet application for appropriate descriptive and correlational analysis using SPSS V 26 to determine the relationship of the variables, data were analyzed, and recommendations for research objectives were produced.

2.6. Ethical Consideration

The survey questions were handed to volunteered participants who signed a consent form. Stating that the purpose of the study is fully educational, and that whatever they have stated must be kept confidential and anonymous. Also, the treatment of data collected is adherent to the school data privacy statement.

3. Results and discussion

The objective of this study is to observe the relationship of Cross-Training Program to Employees' Retention in selected restaurants in Cabanatuan City. As part of the data collection procedure, the researcher asked the 125 respondents a series of questions on their views in relationship of Cross-Training Program and Employees' Retention. The total number of questions is 20, divided into two sections: Cross-Training Program and Employees' Retention.

The study's findings were subjected to normality testing, which revealed a non-normal data distribution. If the normality test is performed on a non-normal distribution, Spearman Rho correlation must be employed. (See Table 1: Test of Normality using Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk). With a p value of less than 0.05, alongside with the normality test, the researcher conducted a reliability test that resulted to a Chronbach Alpha with the value of .90 (see Table 3: Reliability Test Results)

Table 4 shows the demographic profile of the respondents gathered by the researcher. Most respondents were 23-26 years old with 48 respondents, equivalent to 38.4% of all respondents, followed by 27-30 years old with 42 respondents, equivalent to 33.6% of all respondents, 18-22 years old with 35 respondents, equivalent to 28.0%.

Table 4 Frequencies Analysis for Age

Age	N	Frequency (%)	Rank
18-22 years old	125	35 (28.0%)	3
23-26 years old	125	48 (38.4%)	1
27-30 years old	125	42 (33.6%)	2

A descriptive analysis was conducted to determine the Cross-Training Program in selected restaurants Cabanatuan City as perceived by employees of the said establishments, as shown in table 5. Table 5 shows that the respondents constantly “strongly agree” when expressing their insights about the Cross-Training Program with a mean score rating of $\mu=3.7672$. CTP5 had the highest mean rating of $\mu=3.83$ indicating that respondents “strongly agree” with the statement “Cross-Training program can be used for employees across almost all industries and positions”. Also, the respondents observed “strongly agree” for the items, CTP1 ($\mu=3.76$), CTP2 ($\mu=3.73$), CTP3 ($\mu=3.78$), CTP4 ($\mu=3.84$), CTP6 ($\mu=3.79$), CTP7 ($\mu=3.79$), CTP8 ($\mu=3.71$), and CTP10 ($\mu=3.82$) and the statement CTP9 got the lowest mean rating ($\mu=3.67$).

Table 5 Descriptive Statistics of Cross Training Program

	STATEMENT	N	MEAN(μ)	STANDARD DEVIATION (SD)	VERBAL INTERPRETATION (VI)
CTP1	Cross training programs improve my skills as an employee	125	3.76	0.434	STRONGLY AGREE
CTP2	Cross training can increase flexibility within an organization	125	3.73	0.447	STRONGLY AGREE
CTP3	Cross training may reveal my hidden talents as an employee	125	3.77	0.460	STRONGLY AGREE
CTP4	Cross training program helps me to understand how the business runs at all levels	125	3.84	0.402	STRONGLYAGREE
CTP5	Cross training can be used for employees across almost all industries and positions	125	3.83	0.375	STRONGLY AGREE
CTP6	Cross training program will make me prepared as employee for what circumstances may arise	125	3.79	0.427	STRONGLY AGREE
CTP7	Cross training will help me as employee with better team collaboration	125	3.79	0.408	STRONGLY AGREE
CTP8	Cross training increased my internal mobility as an employee	125	3.71	0.489	STRONGLY AGREE
CTP9	Cross training is another risk to employees becoming generalists and losing their specialized skills or knowledge	125	3.67	0.606	STRONGLY AGREE
CTP10	Cross training will improve my efficiency as an employee	125	3.82	0.383	STRONGLY AGREE

	TOTAL	125	3.7672	0.30421	STRONGLY AGREE
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A descriptive analysis was conducted to determine the Employees' Retention in selected restaurants Cabanatuan City as professed by employees of the said establishments, as shown in table 6. Table 6 shows that the respondents constantly "strongly agree" when expressing their view about the Employees' Retention in selected restaurants Cabanatuan City with a mean score rating of $\mu=3.6472$. ER1 had the highest mean rating of $\mu=3.78$ indicating that respondents "strongly agree" with the statement "I want to stay because I am able to reach my full potential in this organization". Likewise, the respondents observe "strongly agree" for the statement ER2 ($\mu=3.75$), ER3 ($\mu=3.72$), ER4 ($\mu=3.66$), ER6 ($\mu=3.58$), ER7 ($\mu=3.62$), ER8 ($\mu=3.62$), ER9 ($\mu=3.57$), ER10 ($\mu=3.69$) while statement ER5 has the lowest mean rating $\mu=3.47$.

Table 6 Descriptive Statistics of Employees' Retention

	STATEMENT	N	MEAN(μ)	STANDARD DEVIATION (SD)	VERBAL INTERPRETATION (VI)
<i>ER1</i>	I want to stay because I am able to reach my full potential in this organization	125	3.78	0.473	STRONGLY AGREE
<i>ER2</i>	I choose to stay because I am comfortable working with my team members	125	3.75	0.469	STRONGLY AGREE
<i>ER3</i>	I make up my mind to stay because I get timely feedback from my manager	125	3.72	0.502	STRONGLY AGREE
<i>ER4</i>	I 'am determined to stay because I have a clear understanding of my career path here	125	3.66	0.507	STRONGLY AGREE
<i>ER5</i>	I commit to stay because I have been timely promoted in this job	125	3.47	0.576	STRONGLY AGREE
<i>ER6</i>	I decided to stay because I like coming to my work everyday	125	3.58	0.612	STRONGLY AGREE
<i>ER7</i>	I choose to stay because my opinions are valued and considered	125	3.62	0.577	STRONGLY AGREE
<i>ER8</i>	I decided to stay because I see myself working here in the next five years	125	3.62	0.534	STRONGLY AGREE
<i>ER9</i>	I choose to stay because I feel wanted as an employee	125	3.57	0.699	STRONGLY AGREE
<i>ER10</i>	I decided to stay because I feel that I'm growing professionally	124	3.69	0.516	STRONGLY AGREE
	TOTAL	125	3.6472	0.37665	STRONGLY AGREE

The objective of this study was to observe the relationship of Cross-Training Program to Employees' Retention in selected restaurants Cabanatuan City. As shown in Table 7, indicates that the Cross-Training Program has a significant relationship with Employees' Retention ($p < .05$). The results of Spearman's rho Correlation Coefficient show that the Cross-Training Program has a positive correlation with Employees' Retention, with $r_s = .580$ correlation value. As a result, the decision must be accepted.

Table 7 Correlation Analysis of Cross-Training Program and its relationship to Employees' Retention

Variables	n	r _s	Sig.(p-value)	Hypothesis	Decision	Interpretation of the Strength of Correlation
Employees' Retention	125	0.580**	0.000	H ₁	Accepted	Moderate Positive Correlation

4. Discussion

It is evident that this study's findings on the Cross-Training Program and its connection to Employee Retention in selected restaurants Cabanatuan City indicate that it is moderately beneficial for the staff members who are now employed there. The Cross-Training Program is a very useful and important tool for every firm, the researcher find. It assists staff members in simplifying their work and being better equipped for unexpected situations that may happen inside the company. Additionally, it improves the quality of the job that they produce and further fortifies the bonds amongst the employees. It is clear from evaluating the relationship between the cross-training program and employees' retention (H₁) that there is a substantial association between the two.

The Cross-Training Program can be used for any business, not just the food industry, according to the study's findings. It can also be used for every role in a variety of companies. Not everyone is equally skilled, especially those who are just starting out. Training is necessary to help people discover their hidden abilities and talents and helps them become more productive workers. Because some employees don't fully understand different jobs, it helps them be more adaptable. It broadens their understanding of the range of positions they might hold inside the company. Additionally, it aids in a new employee's understanding of how the company they joined functions and moves them to a role they passionate about and they will become aware how day to day operations being done.

They added that the Cross-Training Program serves as a safety net for all employees in case of unfavorable circumstances, such as the current pandemic, which forces food establishments to reduce staff, or when an employee becomes ill and is unable to complete their assigned tasks. In such cases, the trained staff members can perform other necessary tasks. Furthermore, the Cross-Training Program can improve team dynamics in addition to just improving abilities. Additionally, it develops their leadership skills and helps them become better leaders so they can motivate others.

According to the answers, continuing to work for the same firm aids in their achievement of goals and allows them to further showcase their talents. Additionally, continuing to work can help them develop professionally. As they gain experience, their work ethic shapes them into professional workers. Furthermore, workers viewed one another like family when they were at ease getting along with their coworkers, particularly when they weren't aware of the hazardous environment around them. They decided to stay since they don't want to meet new people and they think it will be hard to get another work. It's also been observed that receiving recognition, a promotion, and recognition as an employee is sufficient incentive for workers to remain with the company and report for duty each day since it inspires them to put in more effort and makes their jobs more enjoyable. Furthermore, because they are certain of their course of action, opting to remain in the business might help them have a clear knowledge of the career they want for themselves.

5. Conclusion

These days, a pandemic has caused many restaurants in our sector to lay off workers. Therefore, rather than adding staff during busy periods, managers and supervisors should implement a cross-training program to empower their staff members. Additionally, it improves and raises staff productivity and competence in handling the workplace to complete tasks.

Many workers from various restaurants quit their jobs quickly because they feel like they are not progressing in their current positions or are constantly dissatisfied with what they are doing. Employees need to be understood, and trainings can help to keep them in the company. Additionally, one of the reasons they quit their jobs right away is that they don't get along with other employees. In addition, sometimes they feel their work is of no value, that their opinions are ignored, and that they are unable to showcase their skills in other areas. Ultimately, the researcher draws the conclusion that there is a strong correlation between the cross-training program and employee retention. The Cross-

Training Program is a vital tool that the restaurants can utilize to accomplish their objectives since it produces many positive results, including a flexible and organized workplace and skilled, competent staff that is retained.

5.1. Recommendations

A deeper comprehension of the connection between the cross-training program and employee retention was suggested by the researcher. This study demonstrates that restaurants offer cross-training to their staff members, even though it is evident from the study that there is a substantial correlation between the cross-training program and employee retention. The discussion of suggestions derived from a careful analysis of the data is as follows:

It is suggested that more strategies, recommendations, and plans be created, put into practice, and carried out to encourage the various restaurants in Cabanatuan City to carry out Cross-Training Programs to motivate and encourage them to stay in their establishments in order to ensure the ongoing viability of Employees' Retention to their restaurants.

The management can provide its staff with a wider variety of training programs. For instance, they can receive orientation training to learn the fundamentals of the company, compliance training to learn about laws and regulations relevant to their work, product training, leadership training, and other types of training that can help them further develop and maintain their specialized skills even after they have been assigned to another task within the company. It's crucial to consider everyone's circumstances and viewpoints when introducing new training, and this may be accomplished by working with the management team before distributing the training to the staff members.

The research suggests that the restaurant's employees had to be aware of and comprehend the workings of the company at all levels. Staff members in the restaurants can become more adaptable and knowledgeable about a larger range of organizational operations by putting Cross-Training Programs into place. The researcher proposes that workers should value their employment and develop a variety of skill sets as a result. Additionally, having more knowledgeable and productive staff benefits the management.

The Company should hold staff appreciation days, bonuses, and recognition and reward programs as incentive initiatives. It assists them in managing employee retention by encouraging productivity, concentration, and improved work completion, all of which contribute to job satisfaction.

This study will be helpful to future scholars in the subject of hospitality management. It is important for future researchers to remember that they have the option to expand the study's participant count. It is also advised that similar research be done in the future with far better outcomes using this study, and it may also be used as a data collection tool. They will receive information from this on the Employee Retention Program in selected restaurants in Cabanatuan city, as well as the Cross-Training Program.

References

- [1] Ahmad U. Impact of training on employee retention case business school. April 2014. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Umer_Ahmad/publication/263808540_Impact_of_Training_on_Employee_Retention/links/00b4953bed2d1ce4e9000000.pdf
- [2] Bleich C. 6 major benefits to cross-training employees. Edgepoint Learning; 2021. Available from: <https://www.edgepointlearning.com/blog/cross-training-employees/>
- [3] Cobe P. Cross-training staff eases labor crunch. 2018. Available from: <file:///C:/Users/Shaina/Downloads/Cross-training%20staff%20eases%20the%20labor%20crunch.pdf>
- [4] Cvetkovic A. The 7 best hospitality training ideas. Typsy; 2020. Available from: <https://blog.typsy.com/the-seven-best-hospitality-training-ideas>
- [5] Dillon J. Reskilling, upskilling, cross-training: which strategy do I need? Axonify; 2021. Available from: <https://axonify.com/blog/reskilling-upskilling-cross-training-which-strategy-do-i-need/>
- [6] Dunn H. Effective cross-training and its impact. Customer Support & Excellence Blog; 2012. Available from: <https://www.phaseware.com/PhaseWare-Files-blog/bid/12379/The-Pros-and-Cons-of-Cross-Training-in-the-support-center-not-the-gym>

- [7] Furniss W. A cross-trained restaurant staff contributes to a smooth-running business. TigerChef; 2014. Available from: <https://www.tigerchef.com/blog/a-cross-trained-restaurant-staff-contributes-to-a-smooth-running-business/2085>
- [8] HCG. Employee retention strategies: how do you keep good employees from walking away? 2022. Available from: <https://www.myhcg.com/blog/health-insurance/6-post-pandemic-employee-retention-strategies/>
- [9] Hiner E. How training programs impact staff retention. Prolaera; 2016. Available from: <https://prolaera.com/how-training-programs-impact-staff-retention/>
- [10] Insights E. Starting a food business? Hire top-notch staff and cut turnover. The food service turnover crisis: how it's affecting business. 2022. Available from: <https://hospitalityinsights.ehl.edu/starting-a-food-business-staff-management#:~:text=Estimates%20say%20that%20at%20the,high%20as%20130-150%25>
- [11] JOHN REH F. Cross-training employees. Balance Careers; 2019. Available from: <https://www.thebalancecareers.com/cross-training-employees-2275317>
- [12] McIntosh S. 10 steps for effectively cross-training employees. Purplepass; 2019. Available from: <https://www.purplepass.com/blog/10-steps-for-effectively-cross-training-employees/>
- [13] Miller B. Importance of cross training in the workplace. Direct Recruiters Inc; 2015. Available from: <http://www.directrecruiters.com/uncategorized/blog/importance-of-cross-training-in-the-workplace/>
- [14] Miller C. Cross-training employees: ensure you're ready for the unexpected. 2020. Available from: <https://www.mindtools.com/pages/article/cross-training.htm#:~:text=Cross-training%20is%20the%20practice,Billing%20Department%2C%20and%20vice%20versa>
- [15] Mindtools. Cross training: creating a flexible workforce. 2022. Available from: <https://www.mindtools.com/pages/article/cross-training.htm#:~:text=Cross-training%20is%20the%20practice,Billing%20Department%2C%20and%20vice%20versa>
- [16] Mitchell BB. Cross-train employees to improve morale and retention. 2021. Available from: <file:///C:/Users/Shaina/Downloads/Cross-Train%20Employees%20to%20Improve%20Morale%20and%20Retention.pdf>
- [17] Priyansha M. What are the benefits of cross-training employees? The HR Digest; 2018. Available from: <https://www.thehrdigest.com/what-are-the-benefits-of-cross-training-employees/>
- [18] Read MIN. Cross-training: creating a flexible workforce. Mindtools; 2012. Available from: <https://www.mindtools.com/pages/article/cross-training.htm#:~:text=Cross-training%20is%20the%20practice,Billing%20Department%2C%20and%20vice%20versa>
- [19] See A. How to run an employee cross training program. 2008. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1109/mcg.1986.276821>
- [20] Siebenaller A, Cataldo L. Employee retention strategies during the Great Resignation. Harver; 2021. Available from: <https://harver.com/blog/employee-retention-strategies/>
- [21] Thoma A, Eaves FF. The pros and cons of the PROs. Aesthetic Surgery Journal; 2018. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/asj/sjx265>
- [22] UniFocus. Cross-training hospitality staff: a key strategy for managing through the post-COVID-19 recovery. The case for cross-utilization. 2020. Available from: <https://www.unifocus.com/blog/cross-training-hospitality-staff-post-covid>